

IMPACT OF FINANCIAL LEVERAGE AND OPERATING LEVERAGE ON PROFITABILITY OF SELECTED FMCG COMPANIES IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to study and understand the effect of operating leverage and financial leverage on the profitability of FMCG over 10 years. (2013-2022) for 5 top FMCG selected companies based on Enterprise Value. This research has employed 3 independent variables (Operating Leverage, Interest Coverage ratio, Debt asset ratio) and 1 (One) dependent variable (Cash Profit Margin) as a measure of financial performance. The analysis of the result shows that debt asset ratio and interest coverage ratio is having a negative relationship) with Cash Profit Margin while Operating Leverage is having a positive relationship with the Cash Profit Margin. Based on these the researcher recommend that the firm should have the optimal level of debt finance to ensure the optimal utilization of the firms' assets and the management should also monitor the interest charged on debt financing to avoid the liquidity problem.

KEYWORDS: Enterprise Value, Financial Leverage, Operating Leverage, Financial Performance, FMCG Sector.

INTRODUCTION

A firm can make use of alternative sources of finance which are having different costs. Some have a fixed bearing rate of return (Debentures and Preference capital) while some are having varying rates of return(Equity share capital). Leverage is the employment of an asset/source of funds for which a firm pays a fixed rate of return. What level of debt should a firm employ to have optimal utilization of assets is a question which every researcher wants to know. If the firm is employing high debt, it means that there is more risk to the outsiders as the availability of margin of safety of the funds is very less while if the firm is employing lower debt then the benefit of equity trading is not much available to the owners of the firm. So the firm should try to keep its capital structure at an optimal level.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK/LITERATURE REVIEW

Khushbakht T. (2013) has examined that degree of financial leverage is having a positive relationship with ROA while the degree of operating leverage is having a negative relationship with ROA. In the end, the researcher has concluded that there is no significant effect of operating and financial leverage on ROA, ROE, ROI, and EPS.

Enekwe, C., Chinedu, I., Agu, Charles, I., & Eziedo, K. (2014) examined the debt-equity ratio and total debt ratio is having a negative relationship with ROA while interest coverage ratio is having a positive relationship with ROA. In this study, it was concluded that none of the selected independent variables is having a significant impact on the profitability of the company.

RESEARCH GAP

After going and conducting an overview in respect of the studies undertaken in the context of leverage and financial performance it was found that most of the authors have just contributed by analysing the impact of financial leverage on financial performance, that too, with old torn-out variables. In this

study, an attempt has been made to undertake the impact of both (financial and operating leverage) on financial performance with new variables.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To measure the effect of Financial Leverage on the Profitability of the selected FMCG and Electronics companies.
- 2) To measure the effect of Operating Leverage on the profitability of the selected FMCG and Electronics Company.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

There are two types of leverage:

- 1) **Operating Leverage:** Operating leverage can be defined as a firm's ability to utilize the fixed operating cost to understand the effect of changes in sales on earnings before interest and tax.
- 2) **Financial leverage:** Financial leverage relates to the financing activities of a firm. The firm can raise funds from different sources. Some have a fixed rate of return and some have a variation in return. Financial leverage refers to the ability of the firm to use fixed financial charges to magnify the impact of changes in earnings before interest and tax on earnings per share.

There is another variation of leverage i.e., **combined leverage** (combination of operating leverage and financial leverage). It measures the overall effect of fixed operating costs and fixed financial charges on the profit available to the equity shareholders. As far as this study is concerned the researcher has undertaken the research study for financial leverage.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sampling Design: This method is based on a stratified sampling method as the strata belonging to FMCG Sector are being formed.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

This study is related to FMCG. The ex-post facto research is being used in this research as it involves the events which have already taken place and it cannot be manipulated.

SAMPLE SIZE

The selected sample is based on 5 FMCG Companies (having the highest enterprise value) for a period of 10 years (2013 – 2022).

The name of the selected FMCG companies is mentioned below:

- 1) Hindustan Unilever Ltd.
- 2) ITC Ltd.
- 3) Nestle India Ltd.
- 4) Dabur India Ltd.
- 5) Britannia Industries Ltd.

DATA COLLECTION METHOD

Entire data is collected from the financial statements of the selected companies available on official websites and the ACE Knowledge Portal.

DATA ANALYSIS METHOD

The data is analyzed by calculating Descriptive statistics, Correlation Coefficients, and Regression. The software used to analyze the above research study is MS EXCEL 13 and SPSS.

TIME PERIOD OF THE STUDY

Data for the period (2013- 2022) is used for this research study.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. This study is purely based on secondary data and the time period taken is of 10 years only.
2. More variables as a measure of calculating financial performance and financial leverage can be taken into account.
3. Apart from these, various external factors are having an impact on the profitability of the firm.

SELECTION AND DESCRIPTION OF THE VARIABLES

A total of 4 variables are considered in this research study to analyze the effect of financial leverage on the profitability of the company.

1. INTEREST COVERAGE RATIO

This ratio measures the debt servicing capacity of a firm from fixed interest on long-term loans concerned. This ratio indicates the extent to which a fall in EBIT is tolerable in such a way that the ability of the firm to service its interest payments would not be adversely affected.

It is calculated as:

Interest coverage ratio=EBIT/Interest.

2. DEBT ASSET RATIO

These ratios measure the amount of assets that are being financed by outsiders. A high ratio indicates that the majority of assets are financed by the outsiders and thus it creates more risk to the outsiders. Whereas a low ratio indicates that most are the assets are being financed through owners' funds and thereby providing security to the creditors.

It is calculated as:

Debt Asset Ratio-Total Debt/Total Assets

3. CASH PROFIT MARGIN

Cash profit margin, also known as operating cash flow margin, is a financial metric that measures a company's ability to generate cash from its core business operations relative to its total revenue. It provides insights into how efficiently a company is converting its sales into cash, which is crucial for sustaining and growing the business.

Cash Profit Margin = Operating Cash Flow / Total Revenue

The above Chart depicts the flowchart for measuring the impact of different variables.

FORMULATION OF HYPOTHESIS

H₀: There is no significant effect of the Interest Coverage ratio & Debt Asset Ratio on the Cash Profit Margin of selected FMCG Companies.

H₁: There is a significant impact of Interest Coverage Ratio & Debt Asset Ratio on the Cash Profit Margin of Selected FMCG Companies.

H₀: There is no significant effect of Operating Leverage on the Cash Profit Margin of selected FMCG Companies.

H₁: There is a significant impact of Operating Leverage on the Cash Profit Margin of Selected FMCG Companies.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Firstly, descriptive statistics were applied to describe the relevant aspects of operating and financial leverage and provide detailed information about each relevant variable used as a measure of financial leverage. A correlation was used to know the strength of the relationship between different variables which are used in these research studies while regression analysis was used to know the effect of selected independent variables on the profitability of selected companies.

The model used was multiple regressions which are described as follows:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 + \dots + E_i$$

Where,

Y=Dependent variable of company

X=Independent variable of the company

B₀=Intercept for X variable of the selected company

B₁, B₂, B₃= Coefficient for independent variable X₁,X₂,X₃ respectively

E_i=Error term

Fitting the above model into these research studies the model is as follows:

$$(CPM)_{yt} = b_0 + b_1(ICR)_{yt} + b_2(DAR)_{yt} + E_i \text{ -----(1)}$$

$$(CPM)_{yt} = b_0 + b_1(OL)_{yt} + E_i \text{ -----(2)}$$

Where, CPM = Cash Profit Margin

ICR=Interest Coverage ratio

DAR=Debt Asset Ratio

OL = Operating Leverage

Ei=Error term

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

FIGURE 1.1: CASH PROFIT MARGIN (MEAN)

EXPLANATION

From the above table, it can be seen that ITC Ltd. is having the highest CPM while Britannia Industries Ltd. is having the lowest CPM.

FIGURE 1.2: INTEREST COVERAGE RATIO (MEAN)

From the above figure it can be seen that the average of Interest Coverage Ratio is highest in Britannia Industries Ltd. while it is lowest in Nestle India Ltd. On a prior view it suggests that the burden of interest paying capacity for Britannia Industries Ltd. is highest while it is lowest for Nestle India Ltd.

FIGURE 1.3: DEBT ASSET RATIO (MEAN)

From the above figure it can be seen that Britannia Industries Ltd is having highest mean of Debt Asset Ratio while the proportion of debt in comparison to assets is very low (almost negligible) in case of Hindustan Unilever Ltd. and ITC Ltd.

Figure 1.4: Operating Leverage (Mean)

From the above figure it can be seen that operating leverage is highest in ITC Ltd. while it is in negative figures in case of Dabur India Ltd.

TABLE 1: CORRELATION

	<i>Interest Coverage Ratio</i>	<i>Debt Asset Ratio</i>	<i>Operating leverage</i>	<i>Cash Profit Margin</i>
Interest Coverage Ratio	1			
Debt Asset Ratio	-0.317620499	1		
Operating leverage	0.087177332	-0.121817451	1	
Cash Profit Margin	-0.182342657	-0.330832268	0.215196484	1

From the above Correlation Matrix table it can be seen that all the components of financial leverage (Interest coverage ratio & Debt Asset Ratio) are having negative correlation with the Cash Profit Margin. It implies that if more debt is being involved in the capital structure of the FMCG Companies than the interest burden for the debt would increase and hence it would affect the cash operating profit margin of the company. While on the other side, it can be see that the operating leverage is having positive relationship with the cash profit margin of the company it means that the elementary fixed operating cost of the company perhaps improves the cash operating profit earning capacity of the company.

TABLE 3: MULTIPLE REGRESSION

TABLE 3.1: REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL LEVERAGE ON CPM

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.58
R Square	0.34
Adjusted R Square	0.30
Standard Error	3.39
Observations	46

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	18.34	0.75	24.34	0.00
Interest Coverage Ratio	-0.01	0.00	-3.79	0.00
Debt Asset Ratio	-28.85	7.68	-3.76	0.00

From the above regression analysis table, it can be seen that only 34% of the variation in the Cash Profit Margin is been explained by the Interest Coverage Ratio and Debt Asset Ratio – Value for both the independent variable is < 0.05 and hence null hypothesis is rejected suggesting that both the

independent variable is having a significant impact on the profitability of the selected FMCG Companies.

TABLE 3.2: REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF OPERATING LEVERAGE ON CPM

<u>Regression Statistics</u>	
Multiple R	0.31
R Square	0.10
Adjusted R Square	0.08
Standard Error	4.11
Observations	46.00

	<u>Coefficients</u>	<u>Standard Error</u>	<u>t Stat</u>	<u>P-value</u>
Intercept	15.89	0.63	25.18	0.00
Operating leverage	0.20	0.09	2.19	0.03

It can be seen that the operating leverage is having significant impact on the cash profit margin of the selected FMCG Companies as the p – value is less than 0.05 which implies that fixed operating cost should be employed in such a way that it increases the cash operating profit earning capacity of the company.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

With the help of descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analysis it has been found that leverage plays an important role in influencing the financial performance of the company. It has been found that both the financial leverage and operating leverage is having a significant impact on the profitability of the company. Operating leverage enjoys positive relationship while the financial leverage enjoys negative relationship with the Cash Profit Margin of the company. It means that fixed operating cost gives a boost to the operating efficiency of the company which increases the cash operating capacity of the company while the employment of more debt in the capital structure of the company increases the debt burden which on the other side decreases the profitability.

CONCLUSION

This paper explained the study on the impact of financial & operating leverage on the profitability of the selected FMCG companies. Data was collected from the annual reports of & ACE Knowledge Portal of the selected companies for a period of 10 years (2013 -2022). Cash Profit Margin was taken as a dependent variable and interest coverage ratio, debt asset ratio were taken as independent variable. After conducting correlation and multiple regression analysis it was found that debt asset ratio & interest coverage ratio and operating leverage is having a significant impact on the profitability of the selected companies and hence it can be concluded that the employment of the fixed cost plays a vital role in determining the profitability of the company.

REFERENCES

1. Bhagyalakshmi, K. (2016). Leverage analysis in selected Cement Companies. Indian Journal of Research, Volume5 (3), 97-98.
2. Enekwe, C., Chinedu, I., Agu, Charles, I., & Eziedo, K. (2014). The effect of financial
3. leverage on financial performance: Evidence of quoted pharmaceutical companies in
4. Nigeria. Journal of Economics and Finance, Volume 5(3), 17-25.
5. Khushsbakht, T. (2013). "Leverage"-An analysis and its impact on profitability with

6. to selected Oil and Gas companies. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, Volume2 (7), 50-59.
7. M.Y. Khan & P.K. Jain. (2019). *Financial Management: Text, Problems and Cases*, Chennai, India: Mc Graw Hill Education
8. Varsha, V. (2010). *Impact of Leverage on Profitability of Pantaloons Retail India Ltd. Advances in Management*.
9. Vatavu, S. (2008). *The impact of capital structure on financial performance in Romanian listed companies. Procedia Economics and Finance*.
10. Yegon, C., Cheruiyot, J., J.Sang, & Cheruiyot, P. (2014). *The effects of capital structure on firm's profitability : Evidence from Kenya's Banking Sector. Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 5(9), 152-159.
11. Zeb, A., Khan, S., & Iqbal, M. (2016). *Effect of liquidity and Capital structure on Financial Performance : Evidence from Banking Sector. Developing Country Studies*, 6(7), 109-115.

WEBSITES

1. www.google scholar.com
2. www.doaj.org
3. <https://www.acekp.in/>
4. www.bestjournals.in